

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES,
SRINIVAS NAGAR, MUKKA, SURATHKAL,
MANGALORE- 574146

VALUE ADDED COURSE

ON

Disaster Management

DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING

Name of the course:Disaster Management

Aim of the Course:

The aim of the course is to help students acquire an in-depth knowledge regarding disaster risks and contribute to better and more targeted public health based relief following disasters.

Objectives of the Course

On completion of the module, the student will be able to

1. To increase the knowledge and understanding of the disaster phenomenon, its different contextual aspects, impacts and public health consequences.
2. To increase the knowledge and understanding of the International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UN-ISDR) and to increase skills and abilities for implementing the Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) Strategy.
3. To ensure skills and abilities to analyse potential effects of disasters and of the strategies and methods to deliver public health response to avert these effects.
4. To ensure skills and ability to design, implement and evaluate research on disasters

Duration:

Theory: 30 hours

Practical: 20 hours

Evaluation :

Assessment methods:

- Test paper (Objective test, short answers and case scenario and questions) - 30 marks
- Assessment of assignments/skills - 20 mark

The examination will be conducted by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University

Criteria for eligibility to appear for University Exam

- i.80% attendance in theory
- ii.100% attendance in practical

Criteria for pass

In order to pass a candidate should obtain at least 50% marks aggregate including internal Assessment and marks obtained from college examination

Award of Certificate/Diploma

Certificate will be awarded by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University.

The aim of the master programme is The Master has the following four objectives: